

Development of a Semi-Automated Dough Mixer for the Preparation of African Dishes

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Abstract

The manual preparation of some of the African traditional (dough foods) dishes from their respective flours require significant physical efforts and precise techniques to achieve the desired qualities, besides the fact that they are time demanding. The challenges justify some of the reasons for the dwindling in their demands for them, in spite of the societal values or air of respect acclaimed to them by the populace, consumers. To address these limitations, this research explored the development and performance evaluation of a 1.0 kg/h specialized dough mixer for preparing some of the Nigerian traditional delicacies from their respective flours. The machine, basically, comprises a water tank heater unit, prime mover (variable speed electric motor), lift dough mixing chamber, stirrer stanchion, and control system. Tests were carried out on the machine, with samples of garri, pupuru and semo flour, to evaluate its performance. The results revealed that the productivity of the machine varies with the kinds of delicacies to be prepared (rheological properties) The results revealed that attained optimal throughput capacity of 2.88, 2.75 and 4.45 kg/h when used to prepare semo, pupuru and eba from their respectively flours with mixing ratios of 2.87, 1.17 and 2.11, and productivity of the machine varies with the kinds of delicacies to be prepared (rheological properties) It can produce high-quality-lump-free-dough at reduced dough development time with minimum effort. It was concluded that the use of this machine, would effectively alleviate the challenges associated with the manual preparation of and enhance the demand for the traditional delicacies and foster preservation of the cultural heritage.

Keywords—Traditional dishes, Demand, Challenges Cultural heritage, Dough Mixer, Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Pupuru, Eba and Semovita are well known traditional dishes among the people of Nigeria. These dishes are also prominent and are consumed in some other West African sub-region (Benin, Togo and Ghana) (Awoyele, 2021). In many social gatherings in west Africa countries, these dishes are served with prestige in fostering love and cultural heritage between the communities (Chukwurah et al., 2025). These dishes are menu which can be taken anytime of the day with different varieties of soups like vegetables, melon (popularly known as egusi or ede), Okro and many other amazing soups from different tribes in Nigeria (Abulude and Ojediran, 2006). These staples of food are rich in energy and are good sources of food nutrients in the human diet (Kambaska, *et al.*, 2008). The cultural significances of these dishes is further noted by the role they play in preserving the traditions and customs of society where consumed or cherished (Oke, 2018).

Pupuru is a meal made from cassava fermented flour and then pressing them into a smooth, flexible dough. This labor-intensive method produces a soft and fluffy delicacy, which is popular among many Nigerians. Pupuru is frequently served alongside soups such as Banga or Nsala soup, and its texture helps it to absorb the flavors of the accompanying dishes efficiently. Pupuru is high in carbohydrate and contains critical vitamins and minerals, especially when cooked from fresh cassava tubers. However, it is poor in protein, this necessitates the addition of protein-rich soups or stews to complete a well-rounded meal (Saini *et al.*, 2016).

Another well-known dish, eba, is made with garri flour, which is formed from dried and fermented grated cassava tubers. Garri and hot water are combined to create a smooth Eba. Eba's slightly sour taste is a byproduct of fermentation during the making of garri, which gives it its reputation. This dish is popular because it can enhance the flavour of several soups, including okra and egusi soup (Saini et al., 2016). Eba is a good source of dietary fiber and carbohydrate, both of which are good for the health of the digestive system.

this emphasizes the need to eat it with foods strong in protein. (Masih *et al.*, 2019).

Semovita, commonly referred to as Semo, is made from semolina flour, which is derived from durum wheat. Semovita is known for its slightly grainy texture and is often served with a variety of soups, like Eba and Pupuru. Nutritionally, Semovita is a good source of carbohydrates; it provides more protein compared to the other dishes, due to its wheat content. This afore-mentioned factor makes it a more balanced option when paired with protein-rich soups (Saini et al., 2016; Masih et al., 2019).

The cultural significance of these dishes extends beyond their nutritional value. They are often central to communal gatherings, celebrations, and traditional ceremonies, symbolizing hospitality and togetherness. The preparation and sharing of these dishes foster social bonds and cultural identity among the Nigerian people. Furthermore, the versatility of these dishes allows for the incorporation of various ingredients, including vegetables and proteins, to enhancing their nutritional profiles and adapting them to contemporary dietary needs (Saini et al., 2016; Masih *et al.*, 2019).

The production of any of these meals for consumption involves gradual addition of their respective flour to boiling water accompanied with continuous stirring to achieve a smooth, elastic consistency. These dishes require precise preparation techniques to achieve the desired textures and consistency This technique is crucial as it influences the final texture and palatability of the dish. In some instances, where the dough produced is laden with much lumps, the formed doughs are sometimes pounded with mortar and pestle and afterward molded into balls and steamed with boiling water again. This age-long method of preparation of each of these dishes is not only physically exhausting, especially when mixing the dough (Akinyele, 2015). but sometimes causes inconsistencies in quality and texture, and this made it impossible to scale up production while maintaining the desired standards (Ojo, 2017)

Recent advancements in dough mixing technology have introduced innovative approaches to monitor and control the mixing process in real-time. Dough mixers are designed to facilitate the mixing process and ensuring that ingredients are uniformly combined to achieve the desired dough characteristics. However,

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111

most of the existing mixers were not tailor-made for this purpose. Thus, while considering the values attach to these traditional dishes, the need to find means of alleviating the yearning of the populace, keeping the custom intact and preventing these traditional dishes from going into extinction, it becomes imperative to device a system for performing this task. Hence, the research focused on the development of semi-automated dough mixing machine for preparing 1.0 kg of eba, pupuru and senovita (otherwise called semo) dough from their respective flours.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Stainless steel related materials, such as: sheet of 2 mm thick and 50 mm thick shaft, including variable speed motor and its controller were obtained from Owode-Onirin and Alaba Markets, Lagos state. Mild steel angle iron (40×40×4 mm), heating element and screw jack were purchased from Steel stalls along Sacred Cathedral Road, Akure, Ondo state. Samples of the feedstock (Garri, pupuru and semo) were procured within Akure Metropolis, Ondo State

Design Considerations

To facilitate proper selection of materials, the rheological properties of the dishes were put into considerations in the course of designing the dough mixer. Table 1 presents details of the rheological properties of the three African dishes considered.

Table 1: Rheological properties of different samples of flours

Flour	Loose	Bulk	Swelling Index %	Water Absorption (%)	Emulsification (%)	Least Gelation (%)	Solubility (°C)	
	Density (g/cm ³)						30	60
Garri	0.464	0.513	14.3	40	6.41	58.7	3.3	6.21
Pupuru	0.682	0.933	26.05	15.00	6.42	60.00	3.51	6.04
Semo	0.417	0.732	16.03	23.30	9.69	70.00	3.96	5.16

Source: (Rheological properties of the feedstock as determined at FUTA Research Laboratory)

Description of the Machine and its Principle of Operation

The dough mixing machine comprises a water storage tank, dough chamber, variable speed electric motor, stirrer, lift (jack), heating elements, insulator, controls and frame structure.

The dough mixer operation procedure begins when sufficient of volume of cold fresh water is supplied into its water tank through the inlet port on the water storage tank, where boiling of water required for processing the dough would be performed. In the storage tank, the charged volume of water is raised from its initial to the final temperature presets by the control system with the aid of the submersible heating element installed in the water tank. The control system trips off the boiling process in the water storage tank once the heating process attains the preset temperature. With the aid of the non-return valve (outlet tap) mounted on the water tank directly opposite to the cold-water inlet port, the hot water is dispensed into the dough mixing chamber, which is also gradually heated by the surface type heating element positioned underneath it. The measured flour sample is then gradually dosed and the mixture produced stirred with the aid of stirrer fastened to the electric motor shaft,

III DESIGN ANALAYSIS

Estimation of volume of dough mixture and geometric dimensions of mixing chamber.

According to Otegbayo *et al*, (2019), 500 g of yam flour required 1.8 litre (0.0018 cm³) of water to produce a dough characterized with good texture and formability. Therefore, the water to flour ratio used is 1 : 3.44. As a result of this observation, it can be deduced that 1.0 kg of yam flour requires 3.448 kg of water.

Based on the intended production capacity, 1.0 kg per batch of each of the required samples. The volume of each flour (V_{rf}) with swelling index of φ_{sw} %, loading factor of δ_l %, and at waste or loss factor of β_w %, the volume of sample required to achieve the rated capacity (m_s) and of dough chamber were determined with relation described with Equations (1) and (2)

$$V_{rf} = 1.38m_s[(1 + 0.01\varphi_{sw})(1 + 0.01\beta_w)] \quad (1) \quad V_{rf} = \frac{1}{3}h_c(R^2 + R.r + r^2) \quad (2)$$

The volume of water required, including the geometric sizes of the water storage tank, at γ_r % water retention index was determined with Equation (3)

$$V_w = 1.38m_s[(1 + 0.01\varphi_{sw})(1 + 0.01\beta_w)(1 + 0.01\gamma_r)] = \pi r_t^2 l_t \quad (3)$$

Determination of total mass of sample to be charged into the machine.

During processing, not all the charged feedstock tends to exit the discharge chute, certain fraction often clings to the walls of the processing components, leak out through openings and as such, they are often considered as waste. Assuming the fraction of the rated capacity viewed as waste is M_{ws} , the total mass of the flour charged (M_T) into the machine computed with Equation (4)

$$M_T = M_{ef} + M_{ws} \quad (4)$$

In order to cater for splashing or prevent overflow of feedstock during stirring, the mixing chamber was designed with a trough loading factor (Φ) of 30 %. The volume of the dough mixing chamber was determined with equation (5)

$$V_a = 1.3V_{bm} \quad (5)$$

Estimation of the size of the heating element

The dough mixing machine utilized two sets of heating elements, submersible and surface

(i) The submersible type heating element is installed directly inside the water storage tank, and direct in contact with the water. It is used purposely for boiling water required for forming the dough from its respective flour. The water heating process entails raising the temperature of the water from the initial prevailing temperature (t_1) to the required final temperature (t_2). The heat evolved (Q_1) was determined with Equation (6):

$$Q_1 = [m_w c_w + h_s A_s](t_2 - t_1) \quad (6)$$

where: m_w and c_w denote mass and specific heat capacity of water; h_s is the convective heat transfer coefficient at the mean temperature and A_s is the surface area of the water storage tank. When values were substituted, the power rating of the heating element required is 1.954 kW; 2.20 kW was hereby adapted, and

(ii) The surface type heating element is used for heating and maintaining the dough at the required temperature during stirring until it is properly done to prevent sudden drop or unwanted fluctuation in temperature during mixing and stirring of the dough so as to obtain good texture. The size of the heating element (Q_2) required, for this operation was obtained with Fourier's heat conduction relation described with equation (7)

$$Q_2 = \left[m_f c_f + \frac{k.A}{\delta x} \right] (t_3 - t_m) \quad (7)$$

where: m_f and c_f denote mass and specific heat capacity of concerned feedstock; k_s and δx are the conductive heat transfer coefficient and thickness of material of the mixing chamber; δx is thickness of material of the dough chamber and A is the cross sectional area of the dough chamber, and t_3 and t_m preset final temperature attained by dough and average temperature from initial temperature of the flour

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before dosing and hot ware discharge temperature.. When values were substituted, the power rating of the heating element required is 1.875 kW; 2.0 kW was hereby adapted. It is mounted underneath the dough chamber directly on top of the insulated sliding tray

Estimation of the power rating of the electric motor

The dough mixing machine utilizes a variable speed electric motor. It was considered for the design on the basis of the variation in the viscosity (toughness) of the dough as the mixing process progresses. The variation in the toughness of the dough could be attributed to the presence of gliadin and glutenin which form gluten when feedstock containing them is mixed with water The power required (P) for achieving effective stirring of the dough to prevent formation of lumps and seizure of attached stirrer was determined using the modified Equation (8), as described by Rao (2018);

$$P = |mg + \left(\mu \frac{dv}{dy}\right)A + \frac{mv^2}{r}| \times \frac{2\pi N}{60} \quad (8)$$

where: m is the mass of mixture; g is the gravity; μ is the viscosity; A is the surface area of the mixing chamber; v is the velocity of the stirrer; r is the radius of stirrer; N is the rotational speed of motor. When values were substituted, the power rating of the electric motor required is 272.4 W (0.366 hp); 0.5 hp was adapted.

Fabrication of the dough mixing Machine

The dough mixing machine was developed at the Central Workshop of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of Technology (FUT), Akure, Ondo State. Plate 1 presents photograph of the developed shea nut drying machine.

Plate 1: Photograph of the developed dough mixing machine.

Performance Evaluation Parameters

The dough mixer was evaluated, with respect to each of the three traditional dishes considered, based on the throughput capacity and mixing ratio.

Throughput Capacity

The throughput capacity of a machine is the quantity of product a machine or system can process from the charged input per unit time, under specified operating conditions. It is expressed in terms of units per time and indicates the performance capability of the machine or plant, as described in Equation (9)

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$$T_R = \frac{m_f}{t_d} \quad (9)$$

where, T_R is the throughput capacity, m_f is the mass of dough produced and t_d is the time taken to produce a unit mass of the dough with reference to the charged sample.

Mixing Ratio

The mixing ratio is defined as the ratio of quantity of solid sample (flour), the solute, needed to be added to the liquid sample (water), the solvent, to produce dough of desirable quality. In other words, it is the ratio of mass of water to mass of flour; it can be determined with Equation (10)

$$M_R = \frac{m_w}{m_f} \quad (10)$$

where, M_R is the mixing ratio, m_w is the mass of water present in the dough and m_f is the mass of flour used to form the dough.

Preliminary Test

The machine was tested run to effect necessary adjustment arising malfunctioning due to mis-alignment of component(s) or oversight during the machine fabrication /assembly stage. The water tank, equipped with a heating element, was charged with specified quantity of water, in succession, and operated to determine the time required to heat specific amounts of water to the preset boiling temperature from its initial temperature. During the test, the initial temperature of the water, the volume of water, the boiling temperature, and the time taken to reach the set temperatures were measured and recorded with appropriate instrumentations

Experimental Procedure for Performance evaluating of developed dough mixing machine

Required volume of water was charged into the graduated water tank of the developed dough mixer. The temperature regulator, on the developed control system was preset, to desired final temperature, to initiate the heating of the charged cold water to boiling. The non-return valve on the graduated hot water tank was then opened to meter unit volume of water (1.0 litre into the dough mixing chamber. Measured mass (500 g) of the flour (garri, pupuru or semo) sample was gradually dosed into the dough chamber, the variable speed motor was switched on immediately, and regulated, to stir the mixture (flour-water) until the dough is produced. The water temperatures (initial and final), time taken, volume of water required to produce each of the dough and mass of each of the dishes prepared were noted with appropriate instrumentations (digital thermometer, digital stopwatch, measuring cylinder and electronic kitchen scale). The jack (lift), which carries the surface type heating element and centrally positioned the mixing chamber relative to the motor shaft on which the stirrer is mounted, was then lowered to facilitate offloading of the produced dough. The dough chamber and stirrer, were disengaged, cleaned and re-engaged for subsequent operations. This procedure was replicated with 1.5 and 2.0 litres of hot-water respectively. Each of the dough produced was afterward subjected to organoleptic test (sensory evaluation). This procedure was also used for preparing the other dishes from their respective flours

Evaluation procedure for the Assessment of the Sensorial Quality of the Dough produced

A 10-trained panel formed with equal number of genders but different age groups and different eating habits was constituted to serve as judges for evaluating the sensorial quality of each of the delicacies produced with the developed dough mixing machine. The judges were selected from students of Department of Food Science Technology (FST) of The Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA). Questionnaires were administered to the panelists. Samples of each of the respective dishes, prepared were served to the panelists and asked to grade the acceptability of the dough (eba, pupuru and semo) through their sense organs, with reference to the sensorial properties detailed in the Questionnaires

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115

before them. The overall acceptability of these three dishes were rated on the bases of 9-point hedonic scale ranging from 1(extremely dislike) to 9 (extremely like)

IV RESULTS AND DISCURSSIONS

Table 2 presents the volumes of each dough and total volume of the mixing chamber required for preparing them from their respective flours.

Table 2: Total Volume of the Mixture.

Samples	Volume of mixture before swelling $V_{mb} (x 10^{-3} m^3)$	Volume of mixture after swelling, $V_{ma} (x 10^{-3} m^3)$	Actual Volume of Mixture, $V_a (x 10^{-3} m^3)$
Garri	2.65	3.94	5.12
Semo	1.85	2.80	3.63
Pupuru	1.46	2.39	3.10

From Table 2, it was observed that garri has the highest volume. hence, the final volume of garri was selected and considered as the volume of mixing chamber required Table 3 presents the results of the preliminary test

Table 3: Time required to boil a given amount of water and boiling temperature

Volume of water(L)	Initial temperature (°C)	Boiling Temperature (°C)	Time (mins)
1	28.0	97.42	8.45
2	28.2	98.56	17.30 8.45
3	28.2	98.56	32.32 15.02

The results of the test, as shown in Table 3, indicated that the time required to raise the charged volume of water to the required temperature varied with the charged volume. It was observed that the time taken to attain the same temperature increases as the charged volume (mass) rises. The increase in the time could be attributed to reduction in the collision velocities caused by the increase in the number of particles (mass) sharing same unit of energy, as the power rating of the heating element is fixed.

Table 4, 5 and 6 present the experimental results of the developed mixing when it was used to prepare the three dishes (eba, pupuru and semo) from their respective flour at three volumes of water

From Tables 4 – 6, the results revealed that the machine attained its individual optimal performance, for each of the dough preparation (eba, pupuru and semo), with a mixing ratio of 2.11, 1.15 and 2.87 when mixed with 1.5 litre of water. The machine attained the individual throughput capacity of 4.45, 2.75 and 2.88 kg/h when used to produce each of the dishes. it was observed that the machine attained the highest/best productivity with eba dough and least with pupuru. The optimal increase in the productivity with Eba could be attributed to its ability to possess the lowest values of least gelation concentration (LGC) and density, and the highest solubility couples with the lowest LGC, as feedstock with a low value of LGC takes little time to galantine; also, substance characterized with lower value of density possesses high hydration capacity; this effect also accounted for the increase in the solubility of Eba dough as the temperature increase

Table 4: Performance evaluation results with 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 Litre (0.001m³) of water for *Eba* dough preparation.

S/N	Volume of water (x 0.001m ³)	Mass of flour (g)	Mixing Time (min)	Initial Temp of flour (°C)	Final temp of dough (°C)	Mass of Mixture (g)	Mixing ratio	Productivity (kg/h)
1		500	2.32	31.2	50.8	1310	1.62	6.97
2	1.0	500	2.41	31.2	51.2	1315	1.63	6.90
3		500	2.24	31.2	51.9	1300	1.60	7.00
Average			2.32	31.2	51.3	1312	1.62	6.98
			3.25	31.2	55.9	1545	2.09	4.43
2	1.5		3.33	31.2	55.5	1560	2.12	4.45
3			3.20	31.2	54.8	1555	2.11	4.48
Average			3.26	31.2	55.4	1553	2.11	4.45
1			2.10	31.2	58.9	2804	4.61	8.54
2	2.0		2.15	31.2	58.5	2810	4.62	8.54
3			2.12	31.2	57.8	2806	4.61	8.55
Average			2.12	31.2	58.4	2806	4.61	8.55

Table 5 Machine evaluation with 1.0 and 1.5 Litres (0.001m³) of water for pupuru dough preparation

S/N	Volume of water (x0.001m ³)	Mass of flour (g)	Mixing Time (min)	Initial Temp of flour (°C)	Final temp of dough (°C)	Mass of Mixture (g)	Mixing ratio	Productivity (kg/h)
1		500	4.50	29.8	68.8	1065	1.13	4.70
2	1.0	500	4.54	29.8	72.4	1068	1.14	4.69
3		500	5.01	29.8	70.2	1072	1.14	4.57
Average			4.55	29.8	70.4	1068	1.14	4.69
			5.57	29.8	70.8	1068	1.14	2.73
2	1.5		5.54	29.8	72.4	1073	1.15	2.75
3			5.65	29.8	72.8	1080	1.16	2.75
Average			5.58	29.8	72.0	1074	1.15	2.75

Table 6 Machine evaluation with 1.5 litres (0.001m³) of water for semo dough preparation

S/N	Volume of water (0.001m ³)	Mass of flour (g)	Mixing Time (min)	Initial Temp of flour (°C)	Final temp of dough (°C)	Mass of Mixture (g)	Mixing ratio	Productivity (kg/h)
1		500	4.52	32.2	82.6	1795	2.59	22.13
2	1.5 (dry)	500	4.55	32.2	83.3	1790	2.58	21.84
3		500	4.58	32.2	85.7	1798	2.60	21.62
Average			4.55	32.2	83.9	1794	2.59	21.89
1		500	40.28	32.2	88.6	1929	2.86	2.86
2	1.5(paste)	500	40.22	32.2	89.3	1934	2.87	2.87
3		500	40.16	32.2	90.7	1940	2.86	2.89
Average			40.22	32.2	89.5	1934	2.87	2.88

These results aligned with the findings of Abu *et al.* (2005) that a lower least gelation concentration suggests a better gelling capacity; Akintayo *et al.* (1999) that the lower the LGC, the better the gelating ability of the protein ingredient; a low density of feedstock (flour) will result in the largest water absorption capacity per unit mass of feedstock and the largest dough volume per mass of the feedstock; Suresh *et al.* (2015) that flour with high water absorption may have more hydrophilic constituents such as polysaccharides. Protein has both hydrophilic and hydrophobic nature, and therefore they can interact with water in foods; Sreerama *et al.* (2012) that high absorption capacity value can be attributed to presence of many hydrophilic components contained in foods such as carbohydrate (especially polysaccharides), proteins, especially polar amino acid residues, which have high affinity for water molecules, More so, , Awuchi *et al.*, (2021) reported that the larger the granular size the greater the water absorption capacity, however, the reduction in the throughput capacity of the machine when experimented with semo could be attributed to the high value of its density, and least gelation factor or concentration (LGC), which caused it to take longer time to gelated or form dough, despite the fact that it has the highest swelling index (ability to absorb water and swell) among the food items. The reduction in the throughput capacity regarding the processing of pupuru could also be attributed to its increased fat content which impede its solubility, and increase in the dough development time; as buttressed by the findings of Opong *et al* (2015) that presence of

lipids in food items would reduce the water absorption capacity of foods and can, consequently, reduce solubility.

Tables 7 – 9 present the results of the assessment of the sensorial qualities the three delicacies as graded by the panelists constituted

Attributes	Volume of water (Litre)		
	1.0	1.5	2.0
Colour	6	8	2
Taste	8	9	4
Mouldability	6	9	2
Texture	6	8	2
Aroma	8	9	6
Lumps formation	4	2	8
Overall acceptance	6	8	2

Table 8: Results of Sensorial Quality of Pupuru dough prepared with developed mixer

Attributes	Volume of water (Litre)	
	1.0	1.5
Colour	6	8
Taste	4	8
Mouldability	6	9
Texture	4	8
Aroma	6	8
Lumps formation	4	2
Overall acceptance	6	8

Table 9: Results of Sensorial Quality of Semo dough prepared with developed mixer

Attributes	1.5 litre of water	
	1.5 (dry)	1.5 litres(paste) Litre
Colour	2	8
Taste	2	6
Mouldability	2	6
Texture	4	6
Aroma	4	8
Lumps formation	8	4
Overall acceptance	2	6

The results, from Tables 7 - 9 revealed that when prepared with 1.0 litre of water, the three doughs all exhibited coarse texture, low mouldability, and laden with little lumps formation texture, while other qualities like taste, aroma, colour and mouldability are moderately good. These effects could be due to insufficient quantity of water utilized for preparing them which made the food particles (grains) to be partially dissolved as the concentrations of the solutes (food grains) were more than that of the solvent (water). More so, with 2.0 litre of water, the doughs displayed poor quality, as they were all characterized with poor texture, taste, mouldability, colour and high lump formation; these effects could be due to the use of excess volume of water which made. However, with 1.5 litres of water, the doughs all exhibited the best quality, as they were all characterized with fine texture, good taste, mouldability, aroma, colour and no lump formation. Plates 2 – 9 present photographs of dough produced regarding the three delicacies (Eba, Pupuru and Semo), from their respective flours (garri, pupuru and Semo)

Plate 2: *Eba* dough formed with 1.0 litre of water

Plate 3: *Eba* dough formed with 2.0 litre of water

Plate 4: *Eba* dough formed with 1.5 litre of water

Plate 5: Wrapped Eba dough formed with 1.5 litre of water

Plate 6: Pupuru dough formed with 1.0 litre of water

Plate 6: Pupuru dough formed with 1.0 litre of water

Plate 7: Pupuru dough formed with 1.5 litre of water

Plate 8: Semo dough formed with 1.5 litre of water using dry flour directly

Plate 9: Semo dough formed with 1.5 litre of water using paste sample

V CONCLUSION

The research focused on the development of a dough mixer for preparing some of the African traditional dishes (eba, semo, and pupuru) from their respective flours. It was developed for the purpose of alleviating the yearning of the masses craving for traditional dishes but found it hard to prepare them as a result of the challenges bedeviling their preparations. A dough mixing machine, which basically comprises the graduated water tank, mixing chamber, variable speed motor, lifting system, heating unit and control unit was developed to alleviate the processing challenge. The choice of selecting of materials for its development was based on factors, such as availability, maintenance and nutritional quality of the feedstock; stainless steel related materials were considered for parts of the machine that are in contact with the dough for optimal hygienic quality. The machine when tested and the doughs produced when subjected to organoleptic tests (sensory evaluation), the result of the performance evaluation revealed that it has productivity of 4.45 kg/h for eba, 2.88 kg/h for semo and 2.87 kg/h for pupuru dough from their respective flours at mixing ratios of 1: 2.11, 1: 1.15 and 1: 2.87. The results of the sensory tests revealed that each of the dishes would exhibit its best quality when mixed with appropriately quantity of water. This use of this machine, would effectively alleviate the challenges associated with the manual preparation of and enhance the demand for these traditional delicacies.

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122

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